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Research Article

**A RESEARCH TO ASSESS THE DIET AND ITS ASSOCIATED
DISORDERS: DA VINCI'S DINING DISCIPLINE**¹Dr Hira Noor Ahmad, ²Dr Faiza Naeem, ³Dr Ayesha Javaid¹Bhu 83/12 L, ²BHU 81/5R, WMO, ³THQ Kotmomin, Sargodha**Article Received:** December 2018**Accepted:** February 2019**Published:** March 2019**Abstract:**

In scientific history, there is a lot of evidence regarding diet as the source of disorders. The diet of our forefather is always interesting. This research was carried out at Jinnah Hospital, Lahore (September 2017 to July 2018). Leonardo da Vinci, considered universally, was a "universal genius". His basic rules of eating habit are explained in this research study. The excess habit of eating should be avoided. There should be tasted, good smelling and good-looking food along with "Dining discipline". The food rich in water should be used and saturated fat, sugar and salt consumption should be less. Da Vinci eating habits include fibre-rich, fresh and vegetation food.

Keywords: *Diabetes, Hypertension, Metabolic Syndrome, Nutrition and Obesity.*

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INTRODUCTION:

In Florence, Leonardo da Vinci (15 April 1452-2 May 1519). He was a son of Caterina and Piero da Vincic. He worked in Venice, Rome, Bologna and Milan. In France, he passed his last few years [1].

He was a brilliant scholar in Italy. He changed the broad spectrum of arts and sciences through his acquirements. The renowned portrait “The Last Supper” and Mona Lisa, are painted by him. Many people thought him a universal genius [2]. Leonardo was a multi-talented person. He was also a budding nutritionist, polymath zoologist, musician, anatomist and architect. Leonardo da Vinci was a physically fit man, according to some people. They were of the view that he took much care of a vegetarian although rich and was living infamous culinary town Florence. This showed that he loved his life. Many people followed his diet patterns. The culinary and dietary principles of da Vinci that were followed by other people are explained by in this research study [3, 4]. The principles are still considered suitable.

Fresh food:

As compare to prickled and processed food is encouraged by the master. He used fresh bread and limited to beans, grains and vegetables. Their food items have high satiety value and low glycemic index. Spinach, cheese, bread, egg and vegetable sauté would be used by him. He had a great love for living beings i.e. animals. So, he did not use animals as a source of food. Other hand vegetables, de Vinci would have used free-range meat (i.e., the meat of animals grazed on natural grass). However, ‘farmed’ meat (sourced from animals bred in captivity in commercial forms) was not consumed by him. The meat of animals comprised of what they eat [5].

Ambience and approach

- Dining discipline
- Culinary ambience
- ‘listen to your baby’
- Savour smell, taste, texture of food
- Avoid overeating
- Composition
- Vegetarian diet
- Fresh foods
- Fiber-rich foods
 1. Vegetables
 2. Grains
 3. Beans
- ‘free range’ meats may be used
- Cooking style
- Moderate fax intake
- Minimize saturated fat use
- Minimize salt and sugar intake
- Beverages

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Fluid intakes:

He used wine as an essential part of diet. The alcohol content in his wine was very low. To contaminated water source, he used wine as a medicated bacteria-free alternative. More ever, he preferred water intake [6].

Culinary advice:

According to da Vinci, the consumption of sugar and salt should be less and the natural taste of food be enjoyed. He was also restricted to low saturated fat in the diet. This is relevant to the modem as well as ancient science [3, 4]. Baker Stephen Lanzarotta established what he said. Da Vinci diet, based on Leonardo da Vinci mathematical rules of the golden ratio. He suggests a diet that includes 28% fat, 20% protein and 52% carbohydrate [7].

To increase the listening power of the stomach, da Vinci supported diets skills. Through this, taste, smell and texture of food is felt. The meal that stimulates the pentad of senses i.e. touch, taste, olfaction, hearing and sight, is considered an ideal meal.

Dining discipline:

A simple and balanced diet is suggested by da Vinci. He also followed the same diet. This diet was balanced as well as enjoyable. He considered dining discipline and dietary impression essentially [4]. Obesity is caused by meals on the go and fast food. Total caloric consumption is decreased by a relaxed meal is the one in which the intake of food is slow.

Da Vinci suggests students prevent from overeating and eat when required. He preferred eating when there is an instinct thunder. He suggests that we should not lie down with head downward and stomach upward [4]. The master doesn’t care about the quantity and quality of food.

SUMMARY:

The summary of da Vancian diet rules is given below:

- 1- The food having fat or carbon hydrates should be avoided.
- 2- Right preparation: by taking a measure like a companion (combining protein and carbon hydrates example cream, berries, pasta, and tuna etc); the glycemic index of food should be lowered by suitable cooking techniques.
- 3- The use of sugar and salt should be prevented and ingredient should be used with the natural flavour.

- 4- For cooking, fresh ingredients should be used with the natural flavour.
- 5- Wine should not be used between the meals or on empty stomach. Wine should be diluted with water and used in moderation.
- 6- Our food should contain the proper proportion of protein, fat and carbohydrates.
- 7- Foods should be nutritionally dense in proper protein.
- 8- Food should be used with changes
- 9- Use artisanal food products, to have good nutrition, made in small batches with a trained eye and with a holistic view to prevent impact on the environment.
- 10- Leonardo suggested that a person should have sufficient toilet.

Sense	Example
Sight	Colorful fruit/salad
Olfaction	Appetizing smell
Hearing	'Sizzling' grilled food, seafood
Taste/palate	Spices
Texture/touch	Eating with hand

Protein and fats: Butter, walnuts, ricotta, hemp, cottage cheese, sesame seeds, kefir, anchovies, yoghurt, mackerel, lamb, Salmon, eggs, avocados, grass-fed poultry, olive oil, and others.

Carbohydrates: Wholemeal sourdough, cabbage, dark chocolate, kale raw honey, kimchi, winter squash, onions, tomato sauce, tempeh, miso, and others.

Excluded from diet: Soya meat products, soda pop, unfermented soy, hard liquor, fatty seafood, refined sugar, fatty meat, non-artisanal baked goods, shortening, artificial sweeteners, margarine and deep-fried food.

Uncial implication: Even in today's modern world, the rules of the Vancian diet is relevant. Health is improved by relaxed meals, in moderate quality, following dining discipline and stimulating the various sensors. The healthy metabolic constitution is maintained by use of fresh, fibre-rich vegetarian food with less sugar fat and salt. Leonardo da Vinci as well as his diet gain patterns were widely considered universally.

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